

New-gen crypto-Nets

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Abstract

Conceptually, Blockchain technology can be applied to any distributed environment to provide intuitive benefits deriving from information security and replication. To achieve the efficiencies possible in an open global market, the crypto-network must be open and global (i.e., unpermissioned, or public). However, current public crypto-networks have several challenges, including: scalability, throughput, cost, addressability and identification of the parties involved, no governance, price fluctuations and forks. New-gen crypto-nets will solve all of the above challenges, allow for a usable world currency, and allow for a Distributed Operating Environment for general distributed applications (GApps).

	Internet	1 st Generation Crypto-networks	2 nd Generation Crypto-networks
C Communication	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scalable with technology	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Use the Internet	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Use the Internet
A Addressability and Unique Identity	Not good Centralized DNS Registration, no unique identity of users	Not existing One-time anonymous transactions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nodes, devices and users can be uniquely identified
R Replication of data	Not existing	Not good Scalability problems, High cost	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scalable, no cost or very low cost
S Security	Not good SSL added, centralized CAs, centralized DNS Registration	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Encryption and verification	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Encryption, verification and biometric devices

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How Close Are We to an Open Distributed Environment?

Keywords:

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